

Statistical Methods Underlying International Migration Estimates at the Census Bureau

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Abstract. This paper summarizes in a statistical notation the residual method of estimating international emigration and applying it to foreign-born yearly US emigration as one component of the Population Estimates Program. The ideal parameters to be estimated are described in terms of the American Community Survey target population, and formulas for the estimates are given, with attention to how variances of some parts of them based on ACS survey-weighted totals can be estimated. The exercise investigates the application of these estimation methods in single-year increments to ACS PUMS data and finds that there are enough stability issues to provide strong motivation to aggregate multi-year data before applying the method. The rates of imputation of the relevant ACS variables (place-of-birth, year-of-entry, citizenship) are found to be large enough to be an important source of variability of the emigration numbers. Some alternative formulations of emigration rate estimates for multi-year aggregated data are also given.

Key words. demography, Population Estimates Program, American Community Survey, variance estimation

1 Introduction

The goal of this paper is to explain for an audience of research statisticians material that is well known to demographers at the US Census Bureau. The juxtaposition of statistical research questions in a demographic context is a useful way to present the principles of existing demographic methodology in preparation for further development and to introduce the steps needed to provide estimates of variance. The specific focus of the paper is the *residual method of emigration estimation* for the foreign-born US population, as implemented within recent Population Estimates produced by the Census Bureau.

The high-level idea of the emigration-group residual method is that if one can measure the change in the population of a specific set of resident people in a defined geography between two time points and account for those who have died in the interim, then the remainder must have emigrated. The difficult details of implementation relate to data sources. We discuss the concepts involved in residual-based measurement of foreign-born emigration, the formulae currently used to estimate the number of foreign-born emigrants, as

well as the variance and standard errors implied by the surveys used to estimate emigration, along with known issues in those surveys resulting in nonsampling error. We then describe methods implemented or proposed to lessen the estimation errors.

1.1 Program Background

The Continuous Count Study (CCS) research focuses on how the Census Bureau can use and expand the source of administrative records data to produce population and other estimates on an ongoing basis. The CCS has two parts. The first part quantifies the administrative data utility and availability. Building off the use of administrative records in the 2020 Census and the Real-Time 2020 Administrative Record Census Simulation experiment [Brown et al., 2023], the Census Bureau is producing annual administrative record population estimates. . The second part of the CCS is researching population estimation and small area estimation techniques to generate alternative population estimates that can be used to assess the quality and coverage of the administrative record data results. This includes research enhancements to the cohort component method that produces our population estimates. The paper focuses on the residual method of emigration estimates in the Population Estimates Program (PEP) [United States Census Bureau, 2024a] in such a way as to suggest how to quantify their statistical errors.

PEP provides an annual census-based update of national, state, and county populations cross-classified by age-group, sex, race, and ethnicity. The important population estimates provided by PEP are used by many surveys within and beyond the Census Bureau as calibration targets. The estimates are based on the most recent decennial census, current American Community Survey (ACS) estimates, Puerto Rican Community Survey estimates, together with birth and death records collected from state and county governments, foreign registers of US-born persons, Puerto Rico, and military net change information from the Defense Manpower Data Center (DMDC) [United States Census Bureau, 2024b].

The aim of the CCS is to research and develop methods for creating a data product on an annual basis for lower geographic levels than is currently available for population totals cross-classified by limited race and ethnicity categories and by adult and non-adult age splits. The CCS combines work of multiple research subgroups, one of which – the Cohort Component subgroup that we work under – specifically focuses on demographically defined sources of population change.

1.2 Demography Background

The discipline of demography is broadly concerned with enumerating populations and population changes, using data from governmental administrative sources, vital records, and surveys and censuses. This eclecticism with respect to data sources results in a lesser emphasis on the quantification of estimation errors than statisticians would prefer. Another difference between the way demographers and statisticians formulate estimation problems relates to the distinction between parameters to be estimated and the statistical population-based estimators used to estimate them. This distinction is largely terminological in the demographic context, but results in different ways of thinking about estimation problems. For example, the statistician would define the rate of emigration within one calendar year from a specified population as a parameter given by θ . However, this θ may not be directly estimable from an accessible survey on its target population, while an analogous parameter θ_{proxy} might be estimated from available surveys or administrative records applicable to somewhat different populations. The demographers sometimes call these populations *proxy populations* or *proxy universes*. The primary example of this concept and estimation strategy in the

present context of foreign-born emigration rates is discussed in detail following formula (12) in Section 2.5.

Statisticians would say that estimates of θ based on a proxy population have two distinct levels of error, one a nonsampling or approximation error reflecting the difference between θ in the desired target population and θ_{proxy} in the ideal proxy population, and another based on sampling or other measurement error in using accessible data to estimate the proxy-population ratio.

Demography begins with a general balance equation

$$(\text{Population Next}) = (\text{Population Previous}) + (\text{Births}) - (\text{Deaths}) + (\text{Net Migration}). \quad (1)$$

This formula applies over a specified interval of time to any subpopulation defined by criteria not changing with age or time. Births and deaths (both non-negative integers) are derived from vital-records registers, which are generally very accurate in the US but are available only after a time delay, with some classification errors, when cross-classified by fine geography or racial/ethnic characteristics. The net migration term (an integer) in the equation is particularly difficult to estimate from data. To begin, migration is broken down by in / out direction:

$$(\text{Net Migration}) = (\text{Immigration}) - (\text{Emigration}). \quad (2)$$

Immigration (a non-negative integer) enumerates persons that move into a geography and emigration (a non-negative integer) those who move out. A second decomposition focuses on the nature of migratory move across national boundaries

$$(\text{Net Migration}) = (\text{Net Domestic Migration}) + (\text{Net International Migration}). \quad (3)$$

Net domestic migration (an integer) is the migration to and from a United States geography and net international migration (an integer) is the migration to and from non-United States geographies. United States in this context is defined as 50 states plus the District of Columbia and at the national level of aggregation, and net domestic migration at the national level is zero by definition.

The problem addressed in this paper concerns the estimation of international migration, which subdivides further. International migration is broken down according to US, Puerto Rican, or foreign birth, and military transfers in and out of the US are handled separately.

$$(\text{Net International Migration}) = (\text{Net U.S./P.R. Born}) + (\text{Net Foreign Born}) + (\text{Net Military Transfers}).$$

Then, for the foreign-born, we decompose migration into emigration and immigration:

$$(\text{Net Foreign Born Migration}) = (\text{Foreign Born Immigration}) - (\text{Foreign Born Emigration}).$$

Military transfers could be decomposed is the same way, but only net figures are available from the DMDC.

2 Current Residual-Based Emigration Estimation Methodology

2.1 Residual Method Concept

In the residual method, we measure a specific population at an initial time point and then also at a subsequent time point, either tracking or projecting deaths in between the two times. The general notion is that any person must either have remained in the population, died, or emigrated, although there is the logical

possibility of having emigrated and moved back within the time interval. The concept from the demography perspective is described in Warren and Peck [1980] and a paper describing some research on this application based on ACS data is given in Leach and Jensen [2013].

Let $s < t$ be two time points at which the populations can be related through

$$N_s = N_t + D_{[s,t]} + M_{[s,t]} \quad (4)$$

and thus the migration component can be solved as

$$M_{[s,t]} = N_s - D_{[s,t]} - N_t \quad (5)$$

Here s is the initial year for which the population is defined, t the reference year up to which the number of emigrants is measured, $D_{[s,t]}$ the number of deaths in the defined population over $[s, t]$, $N_t = N(t)$ the remaining population at time t among the initial population defined at s , and $M_{[s,t]}$ the number of emigrants. Equation (5) exhibits migration as the residual of the original population after accounting for deaths. The only subtlety here is that logically some emigrants might have returned to be counted among N_t , so (5) is a strict identity only if emigrants who returned are counted as though they had never left.

The residual calculation is valid for all subpopulations defined at s with characteristics that do not change by time t . Notationally, we attach a superscript C_s to label the initial population:

$$M_{[s,t]}^{(C_s)} = N_s^{(C_s)} - D_{[s,t]}^{(C_s)} - N_t^{(C_s)}. \quad (6)$$

It follows immediately that this equation for the union of disjoint populations C_s is obtained by adding up the corresponding equations for the separate subpopulations.

There is not generally a data source for the numbers of deaths for populations C_s defined by characteristics (e.g., racial or geographic) at time s . To overcome this obstacle, one typically estimates the number of deaths through the application of life tables. The idea is that

$$E \left[D_{[s,t]}^{(C_s)} \right] = N_s^{(C_s)} \times \left(1 - \ell_{[s,t]}^{(C_s)} \right) \quad (7)$$

where $\ell_{[s,t]}^{(C_s)}$ is the surviving fraction of the group C_s on $[s, t]$ and E is the expected value calculation. In practice, the surviving fraction is aggregated from age-specific survival rates $\ell_{k,[s,t]}$ (for persons aged k at the beginning of the interval $[s, t]$) drawn from life tables relevant to the group C_s , taking account of the ages (and birth cohorts) of population members counted in $N_s^{(C_s)}$.

2.2 Time in PEP and ACS

Population counts in the formulas above are ideally defined at specific instants s, t , but that is not how they are estimated from data sources. The survey-based population counts, such as those estimated from the American Community Survey (ACS), are based on single whole calendar years, or 5 successive years. For single year k of data, one may interpret the survey-weighted count as an estimate of the ideal population at the mid-point of the year, July 1, and this is the convention in PEP.

Index g	Emigration Subgroup
1	Mexican Born Males, Arriving in the last 10 years
2	Mexican Born Females, Arriving in the last 10 years
3	All Mexicans Born, Arriving more than 10 years ago
4	All Canada or Europe Born, in the last 10 years
5	All Asian Born, Arriving in the last 5 years
6	All Other Foreign Born, Arriving in the last 10 years
7	All Other Non-US Non-PR Born

Table 1: Partition of the US foreign born population into subgroups for the purpose of estimating emigration.

2.3 Subpopulations used in Estimating Foreign-Born Emigration

For the purpose of estimation, the foreign-born population ((persons not born in the United States or Puerto Rico) is identified by Place of Birth and by Year of Entry (the most recent year a person has come to reside within the United States). In practice these people are defined by ACS-question responses. The foreign-born population is subdivided into the 7 mutually exclusive groups listed in Table 1. These groups have been chosen because the demographers have some evidence indicating that their yearly emigration rates (the ideal statistical parameters we are interested in estimating) are different, and the groups are large enough for those rates to be estimated.

There are two quirks in this definition of emigration groups. The first is that the definition of group membership changes with time: a member of Group 1 may no longer be a member 3 years later (e.g., if the Year of Entry was 8 to 10 years ago). The second is that the small but non-negligible subpopulation of group 1 and 2 members who emigrate and then return within a few years may change its group membership because of the convention [United States Census Bureau, 2019] that the Year of Entry is interpreted in ACS as the *most recent* year of entry.

2.4 Migration Count and Rate Estimation

Estimation of migration counts follows immediately and naturally from (6) when applying ACS in the framework of Subsection 2.1. The estimate for migration is

$$\hat{M}_{[s,t]}^{(C_s)} = \hat{N}_s^{(C_s),ACS_s} - \hat{D}_{[s,t]}^{(C_s),ACS_s} - \hat{N}_t^{(C_s),ACS_t}. \quad (8)$$

ACS_s and ACS_t express the ACS vintages used to compute each estimate within the equation. From this point on, (C_s) is redefined specifically as $(C_s) = (g, \text{sex}, \text{age} = k)$ as of time s , where g is a group label 1–7 as defined in Table 1. The estimate \hat{N} is directly obtained from ACS microdata, but \hat{D} is not. To obtain \hat{D} , an appeal is made to life tables of yearly age-specific survival rates,

$$\hat{D}_{[s,t]}^{(C_s),ACS_s} = \hat{N}_s^{(C_s),ACS_s} \times (1 - \ell_{k,[s,t]}^{(C_s)}) \quad (9)$$

where

$$\ell_{k,[s,t]}^{(C_s)} = \ell_{k,[s,t]}^{(g,\text{sex})} = \prod_{z=0}^{t-s-1} \ell_{k+z,[s+z,s+z+1]}^{(g,\text{sex})} \quad (10)$$

The number of migrants (and similarly, deaths and population counts) for each group is obtained by summing over the ages and sexes

$$\hat{M}^{(g)} = \sum_{(\text{sex}, \text{age})} \hat{M}_{[s,t]}^{(g, \text{sex}, \text{age})}. \quad (11)$$

The estimated emigration rate as implemented by the U.S. Census Bureau is given

$$\hat{R}_{[s,t]}^{(g)} = \frac{\hat{M}_{[s,t]}^{(g)}}{(t-s)\hat{N}_s^{(g), \text{ACS}_s} - \sum_{k=1}^{t-s} \hat{D}_{[s, s+k]}^{(g), \text{ACS}_s} + \hat{D}_{[s,t]}^{(g), \text{ACS}_s} / 2 - \hat{M}_{[s,t]}^{(g)} / 2}. \quad (12)$$

The formulation given reflects the number of migrants over the years as given in the numerator over a measure of life-years of exposure (i.e., number of years present) in the denominator. A rationale for this formula, leading also to what we believe is an improvement, is given in Section 5.2.

2.5 Proxy Populations for Emigration-rates

Formula (12) ostensibly estimates the ideal statistical parameter $\theta_t^{(g)}$, the emigration-rate for data year $t > 2015$ in the foreign-born emigration-group population g . In fact, as seen in equation (13) below, recent Census Bureau practice has been to estimate this rate as an average of three estimates $\hat{R}_{[a,b]}^{(g)}$ (with $a = 2010$, and $b = 2014, 2015$, or 2016) on the proxy population cohort consisting of the US foreign-born residents alive in group g at the beginning of data-year a and followed for data-years a through b , as seen in (13). The emigration rate for this proxy population cohort is the θ_{proxy} parameter estimated by $\hat{R}_{[a,b]}^{(g)}$. Thus, the current method replaces the desired parameter $\theta_t^{(g)}$ as estimand by the average of three such proxy-population parameters.

There are several ways in which the form of the estimate relates to proxy populations different from the year- t emigration group. First of all, membership in the group is defined from the self-identification of ACS respondents through answers to the ACS questions on Citizenship, Place of Birth and (for the foreign-born, most recent) Year of Entry into the US. Yet many ACS respondents omit one or more of these questions, so that the answers must be ‘allocated’ (by logical inference from answers actually provided to other question) or ‘imputed’ from other ACS respondents providing similar answers (e.g., about location and race or ethnicity) to the ACS respondent omitting answers. Second, although age-specific mortality rates differ for different foreign-born groups especially based on recency of entry into the US, the government does not produce separate life-tables for these groups, instead approximating their mortality rates by the Hispanic life-tables for males and female that are publicly available from the National Center for Health Statistics (NCHS) [National Center for Health Statistics, 2024].

Temporal specificity of the population groups used to estimate emigration differs from the ideal in three main ways. Estimates based on one-year cohorts (with $s = t-1$) in (12) are found to be too noisy for PEP, as is discussed in Section 4. Therefore multi-year $[t-m, t]$ cohorts are used in the estimation. Second, because the group-membership criterion changes over time for individuals, the targets of estimates (12) referring to the group cohort alive at time $s = t-m$ differ from the ideal yearly rates. Third, even the multi-year cohort-based emigration estimates can vary considerably over successive years. The ongoing emigration rate estimate currently (as of 2023) applied by the U.S. Census Bureau averages three cohort-based rate estimates

(12) with initial year 2010 and respective terminal reference years of 2014, 2015, and 2016. That is

$$\hat{r}_{\text{cohort.avg}}^{(g)} = \frac{1}{3} \left(\hat{R}_{[2010,2014]}^{(g)} + \hat{R}_{[2010,2015]}^{(g)} + \hat{R}_{[2010,2016]}^{(g)} \right). \quad (13)$$

The corresponding foreign-born emigration estimate by group g in year t is

$$\hat{M}_t^{(g)} := \hat{N}_t^{(g),\text{ACS}_t} \times \hat{r}_{\text{cohort.avg}}^{(g)} \quad (14)$$

and then the estimate of foreign born emigrants at a national level is $\hat{M}_t \equiv \sum_g \hat{M}_t^{(g)}$.

An alternative version of the emigration rate estimates, that does a more systematic job of maintaining exposure estimates for persons remaining in the respective emigration groups, is given in Section 5.3. Section 5.1 further discusses ways to make the estimates (13) and (14) more time-specific.

3 Survey Variance Estimation

Variances of survey-weighted totals and ratios of them, which occur in the emigration rate estimates (12), can be calculated in a standard way according to ACS *Successive Difference Replication* (SDR) variance methodology [United States Census Bureau, 2014] for totals. To this end, the life-table single-year survival rates entering (12) through $\ell_k^{(\text{sex},\text{Hispanic})}$ in (7), are assumed to be fixed and known. In the ACS, for each person record i in the set \mathcal{R} of respondents, with vector of responses \mathbf{y}_i , comes equipped with a ‘final weight’ w_{0i} together with replicate weights w_{ri} , $r = 1, \dots, 80$ of the form originated by Fay and Train [1995]. The estimate of a population total t_{y_j} of responses $y_{i,j}$ is $\hat{t}_{y_j} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{R}} w_{0i} y_{i,j}$, with replicate estimators $\hat{t}_{y_j}^{(r)} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{R}} w_{ri} y_{i,j}$, $r = 1, \dots, 80$. In SDR methodology, the estimated variance of an estimate $\hat{\theta}$ (total or ratio) with analogous replication calculations, $\hat{\theta}^{(r)}$, $r = 1, \dots, 80$, is given by

$$\widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{\theta}) = \frac{4}{80} \sum_{r=1}^{80} \left(\hat{\theta}^{(r)} - \hat{\theta} \right)^2 \quad (15)$$

with an analogous formula for covariances,

$$\widehat{\text{Cov}}(\hat{\theta}^{(1)}, \hat{\theta}^{(2)}) = \frac{4}{80} \sum_{r=1}^{80} \left(\hat{\theta}_r^{(1)} - \hat{\theta}^{(1)} \right) \left(\hat{\theta}_r^{(2)} - \hat{\theta}^{(2)} \right). \quad (16)$$

For the variance of the emigration total value it should be noted that the two distinct sets of 1-year ACS estimates are assumed to be independent of one another. It follows from the migration equations (8), (9) and (11) that

$$\widehat{\text{Var}} \left(\hat{M}^{(g)} \right) = \widehat{\text{Var}} \left(\hat{N}_s^{(g),\text{ACS}_s} - \hat{D}_{[s,t]}^{(g),\text{ACS}_s} \right) + \widehat{\text{Var}} \left(\hat{N}_t^{(g),\text{ACS}_t} \right). \quad (17)$$

The variance for the first ACS_s term is obtained via SDR as a replicate-based survey-weighted total.

The variance of the ratio $\hat{R}_{[s,t]}^{(g)}$ relies upon an application of the delta method. The delta method in general says for a consistent statistic $\hat{\theta}$ such that $\sqrt{n}(\hat{\theta} - \theta)$ is approximately normally distributed with variance consistently estimated by $\hat{\Sigma}$, that the transformed statistic $f(\hat{\theta})$ is also consistent (for $f(\theta)$ with $\sqrt{n}(f(\hat{\theta}) - f(\theta))$ approximately normally distributed with variance consistently estimated by $[\nabla f(\hat{\theta})]' \hat{\Sigma} [\nabla f(\hat{\theta})]$).

The migration rate estimate of (12) can be rewritten as

$$\hat{R} = \frac{A_1 - A_3}{A_2 - (A_1 - A_3)/2} \quad (18)$$

where A_1 and A_2 are highly correlated quantities originate from ACS_s , and A_3 is defined from ACS_t . The delta method is applied to the vector statistic (A_1, A_2, A_3) where variances are estimated by (15), the A_1, A_3 and A_2, A_3 covariances are 0, and the A_1, A_2 covariances are estimated via (16). The variances for (13) can be obtained using a more complicated (higher-dimensional) delta method, using several independent ACS 1-year estimates from different data years.

4 Study: Emigration Rates based on Single-year Data

The current residual methodology involves an average of multiple historical emigration figures as given in (13). As mentioned in Section 2.5, the ideal target of estimation would be single-year emigration-rates for the separate emigration groups in Table 1. Demographers in the Census Bureau’s Population Division had previously studied estimates based on a single year of data and found them to be much too noisy for use in production PEP estimates. In particular, the single-year emigration numbers estimated in that way are occasionally negative, which is untenable.

The exercise of this section is to investigate the estimates from a single-year application of the foreign-born emigration residual method. To enable public release of the estimates, they are based not on ACS microdata but rather the on Public Use Microdata Set (PUMS) for ACS which is a subsample of the ACS which represents 1% of the U.S. population [United States Census Bureau, 2022]. This we shall reference as ACS PUMS. Because this subsample is about two-thirds of the original 1-year sample, the margins of error are larger than for ACS proper, but not much larger. For purposes of demonstration, the 1-year emigration rate estimates (12) were calculated in Table 2 on an annual basis from the 2010-2011 window to the 2018-2019 window.

Table 2 shows that confidence intervals for emigration rates often contain zero, depending on the emigration group. Negative estimates do occur sporadically. Neither behavior is welcome as the true rate of emigration must always be positive. These occurrences mirror behavior observed in ACS microdata.

It is concerning that the margins of error in Table 2 are often greater than the single-year estimated rates. There are a few possible reasons why this may happen. The first is simply that the residual estimates of emigration, involving differences of small-group survey totals, are very noisy. A second likely possibility, which we can explore, is that allocation (imputation) of variables with missing data within survey responses could distort the microdata and the estimates, and it must be emphasized that the SDR variance estimation methodology does not account for variability due to allocation and imputation.

The weighted groupwise allocation rates in the ACS PUMS relating to Citizenship (CIT), Year of Entry (YOE), and Place of Birth (POB) are given in Tables 3, 4, and 5, respectively. The person records are assigned to emigration groups using data in which missing items have already been allocated or imputed. The status of allocation or imputation is given through the flag variables ‘FCITP’, ‘FYOEP’, or ‘FPOBP’ in ACS PUMS. ACS PUMS relates allocation as a binary flag and does not provide detail as to whether allocations from editing rules versus those that rely upon hot-deck imputation. Allocation of one or more of these variables does not necessarily indicate that a person record has been assigned to the wrong emigration

ACS Year	Emigration Group						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2010→2011	5.8	2.7	(0.1)	6.2	5.6	3.9	(-0.5)
2011→2012	5.4	3.2	1.8	(2.6)	4.7	(-0.9)	(0.4)
2012→2013	(1.4)	(0.0)	(0.0)	4.8	8.1	(-0.7)	0.6
2013→2014	(2.0)	(-2.8)	(-0.7)	9.6	4.1	2.8	(-0.1)
2014→2015	(0.2)	(1.0)	2.5	4.4	4.0	(-1.3)	(0.1)
2015→2016	4.7	(1.5)	1.2	11.1	9.0	(1.2)	1.6
2016→2017	4.2	3.9	3.8	6.0	7.2	(-1.5)	(-0.2)
2017→2018	(2.7)	(3.4)	1.5	8.1	10.3	(-0.2)	0.9
2018→2019	7.5	5.5	3.2	8.9	11.7	2.8	0.6
2010 Size	2.2M	1.8M	7.8M	1.4M	2.2M	4.3M	21.9M

Table 2: Table of ACS PUMS foreign born emigration rates, as percentages, grouped by the emigration groups of Table 1. Any figure whose 90% SDR confidence interval contains zero is given within parentheses. Size of the Emigration Group cohorts is given based on 1-year ACS 2010 data. The notation “2010→2011” is one-year window emigration measurement starting in 2010 and ending in 2011.

group, but it may have been. Citizenship allocation is the most concerning as this variable determines the ‘foreign-born’ characteristic; the YOE and POB variables relate to group assignment. For all three variables, frequent allocation reflects an important source of variability in the emigration-group methodology.

Rates of allocation for YOE and POB variables is comparable to or larger than the migration rates, and the allocation rates are increasing with data-year. Further investigation would be needed to judge if allocation itself is a substantial factor in affecting estimated migration rates. Even if imputation does not result in overall biases, it does likely reflect under-estimated variances.

5 Discussion

This Section discusses challenges within the current emigration-rate estimation method, some proposed fixes, and longer term research questions about this estimation problem.

5.1 Estimating Foreign Emigration with Current Data

We have already raised in Section 2.5 the dual issues that the current method (13)–(14) uses past ACS data (from 2010 to 2016) to estimate groupwise emigration rates, and relies on cohorts that are not fixed with respect to group membership throughout that past time-period. We discuss the first issue – how estimates might be made more timely – in the present subsection, and the improvement of the cohort-based estimates with respect to group-specificity in the following two subsections.

The current PEP method, according to the 2023 methodology document [United States Census Bureau, 2024b] fixes estimates in time based on data values obtained only from the 2010, 2014, 2015, and 2016 1-year

ACS Year	Emigration Group							Nat'l
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
2010	4.9	4.6	4.4	4.2	4.8	4.8	5.0	2.7
2011	4.9	4.5	4.4	4.7	4.0	5.0	4.9	2.6
2012	5.6	5.4	4.5	4.8	4.2	5.3	5.3	3.0
2013	8.4	8.3	6.2	7.1	6.9	7.6	7.2	5.2
2014	9.2	8.7	6.7	7.7	7.6	7.6	7.5	5.5
2015	9.6	9.6	6.8	8.8	8.1	8.5	7.6	6.0
2016	11.8	12.8	8.0	8.8	8.4	9.3	7.8	6.0
2017	14.5	13.7	9.1	9.4	8.5	9.9	8.1	6.3
2018	16.5	16.9	10.6	9.6	8.7	11.2	8.6	6.8
2019	17.3	18.3	12.3	10.5	9.0	11.6	9.5	7.4
2010 Size	2.2M	1.8M	7.8M	1.4M	2.2M	4.3M	21.9M	

Table 3: Weighted allocation percentages of the “citizenship” variable for the emigration groups of Table 1. Size of the Emigration Group cohorts, in persons, is given based on 1-year ACS 2010 PUMS data.

ACS vintages. While the numerical evidence of Section 4 does strongly motivate the aggregation of data across multiple years, there is no reason to suppose that current emigration rates, by group, remain in later years exactly where they were in 2018 (the year of release of 2016 1-year ACS data). Even if POP estimates methodology continues to rely on averaged cohorts from the past, we see no motivation for the method going forward continue to rely on ACS data only up to 2016. Should the three cohorts being averaged have lengths 5, 6, 7 years with their initial year the same as they are in the 2022 methodology document, or maintain the same length 5 for successive years $t - k$, $t - k + 1$, $t - k + 2$ for some choice of initial year a fixed number k of years in the past, or follow some other plan? This choice could be made, during stable times, after statistical experimentation with the variances that would result for these averaged estimators. However, the inclusion of cohorts containing the COVID year 2020 might well be less appealing, so we would recommend searching for principled methods that combine single-year emigration-group data but perhaps avoid specified anomalous years like 2020.

5.2 Derivation and Improvement of Cohort-based Formula (12)

The ratio used in formula (12) to estimate the annual emigration rate for emigration group g has a familiar form from demography and statistical applications involving time-to-event data. The numerator estimates a number of transitions (the number of persons in group g emigrating) over a specified time interval $[s, t)$. The denominator is an estimate of *exposure* or total person-years lived in the US by group g proxy population cohort over the time interval $[s, t)$, analogous to the *total time on test* denominator of the Maximum Likelihood Estimator of a constant hazard rate parameter based on censored data. Section 2 in Chapter 4 of Alho and Spencer [2005] effectively explains these ideas in statistical demography.

What follows is an argument to derive such a formula, to show how a truncated version of the exposure in the denominator yields exactly formula (12), and to argue that the version of the formula without the truncated term is apt to be a better estimate of the migration rate and should be used instead.

The idea of estimating exposure is that for each $k = 1, 2, \dots, t - s$, the $D_{[s+k-1, s+k)} + M_{[s+k-1, s+k)}$

ACS Year	Emigration Group						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2010	15.1	10.9	12.8	8.9	8.2	10.4	8.4
2011	15.0	10.7	12.7	8.9	7.1	10.9	8.9
2012	15.1	11.7	12.8	9.0	7.2	11.3	9.2
2013	19.1	14.8	15.0	11.7	10.0	13.8	12.1
2014	19.8	15.3	15.9	11.9	11.0	13.6	12.6
2015	21.0	17.6	16.2	13.1	11.3	14.8	13.1
2016	23.4	20.1	16.9	13.7	12.3	14.8	13.4
2017	26.3	22.7	19.0	14.7	12.8	15.9	14.2
2018	28.7	26.3	20.9	14.5	12.4	16.3	14.6
2019	31.3	28.4	26.4	15.5	12.4	17.7	21.6
2010 Size	2.2M	1.8M	7.8M	1.4M	2.2M	4.3M	21.9M

Table 4: Weighted allocation percentages of the “Year of Entry” variable for the emigration groups of Table 1. Size of the Emigration Group cohorts, in persons, is given based on 1-year ACS 2010 PUMS data.

persons from the original cohort alive at s who die or emigrate within the year $[s+k-1, s+k)$ will have lived $k-1/2$ years on average in the US within $[s, t)$ if the time of departure or death was uniformly distributed within the year. The people in the original cohort who neither die nor emigrate during any of those years $[s+k-1, s+k)$ live $t-s$ full years on $[s, t)$. The total years lived by cohort members over $[s, t)$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
& (t-s) \left\{ N_s - \sum_{k=1}^{t-s} (D_{[s+k-1, k)} + M_{[s+k-1, s+k)}) \right\} + \sum_{k=1}^{t-s} \{ D_{[s+k-1, s+k)} + M_{[s+k-1, k)} \} (k-1/2) \\
&= (t-s) N_s - \frac{1}{2} (D_{[s, t)} + M_{[s, t)}) - \sum_{k=1}^{t-s} (t-s-k) (D_{[s+k-1, s+k)} + M_{[s+k-1, s+k)}) \quad (19) \\
&= (t-s) N_s - \frac{1}{2} (D_{[s, t)} + M_{[s, t)}) - \sum_{k=1}^{t-s} (t-s-k) (D_{[s, s+k)} - D_{[s, s+k-1)}) - \sum_{k=1}^{t-s} (t-s-k) M_{[s+k-1, s+k)}
\end{aligned}$$

Collecting coefficients of $D_{s, s+k}$ in the summation involving those terms makes this expression

$$= (t-s) N_s - \frac{1}{2} (D_{[s, t)} + M_{[s, t)}) - \sum_{k=1}^{t-s-1} D_{[s, s+k)} - \sum_{k=1}^{t-s} (t-s-k) M_{[s+k-1, s+k)}$$

If in this last expression we write $\sum_{k=1}^{t-s-1} D_{[s, s+k)} = \sum_{k=1}^{t-s} D_{[s, s+k)} - D_{[s, t)}$ and we drop the final summation involving terms $M_{[s+k-1, s+k)}$, we are left with exactly the denominator of formula (12). Thus (12) involves a principled estimation of exposure followed by dropping a relatively small (compared to N_s) but not negligible weighted sum of yearly emigration numbers.

Another way to express the valid exposure estimate (19) is as

$$(t-s) N_s - \frac{1}{2} (D_{[s, t)} + M_{[s, t)}) - \sum_{k=1}^{t-s} (t-s-k) \{ N_{s+k-1} - N_{s+k} \}$$

ACS Year	Emigration Group						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2010	4.3	4.2	3.3	4.6	5.3	4.6	4.0
2011	4.2	4.3	3.3	5.2	4.5	4.7	4.0
2012	5.1	5.1	3.5	5.4	5.1	5.1	4.5
2013	7.1	7.4	5.1	7.7	7.2	7.0	6.4
2014	7.6	7.7	5.3	7.8	7.5	7.1	6.7
2015	8.8	8.6	5.6	9.0	8.0	7.9	7.1
2016	9.2	10.1	5.8	9.0	8.2	7.8	7.2
2017	11.7	11.3	6.7	9.9	8.7	8.3	7.5
2018	13.9	14.2	8.4	11.6	9.9	9.6	9.3
2019	13.6	15.1	8.2	10.2	8.8	9.3	8.3
2010 Size	2.2M	1.8M	7.8M	1.4M	2.2M	4.3M	21.9M

Table 5: Weighted allocation percentages of the “Place of Birth” variable for the emigration groups of Table 1. Size of the Emigration Group cohorts, in persons, is given based on 1-year ACS 2010 PUMS data.

where we have applied the demographic balance equation to the change in cohort population over year $[s+k-1, s+k)$. We simplify this expression by collecting coefficients of N_{s+k} in the final sum, yielding the alternative exposure estimate

$$\begin{aligned}
(t-s)N_s - \frac{1}{2}(D_{[s,t)} + M_{[s,t)}) - (t-s-1)N_s + \sum_{k=1}^{t-s-1} N_{s+k}(-(t-s-k) + t-s-k-1) \\
= \sum_{k=0}^{t-s-1} N_{s+k} - \frac{1}{2}(D_{[s,t)} + M_{[s,t)}) \tag{20}
\end{aligned}$$

We believe the denominator in the PEP estimation formula (12), because of the summation $\sum_{k=1}^{t-s} (t-s-k)M_{[s+k-1, s+k)}$ that was dropped in the extension of (19) to get it, would be more accurately replaced by the estimator version of (20) as a cohort-based estimate of group- g emigration life-years exposure. Dropping a negative term from the exposure estimate makes the denominator larger, artificially diminishing the emigration rate in formula (12).

5.3 Rate Formula based on Yearly Emigration Groups

The Population Division’s approach to estimation of emigration rates, as described in their methodology document and in this paper leading up to formula (14), is based on a group-specific cohort method. However, the definition of the foreign-born Emigration-group cohorts is such that after a few years the group-membership criteria based on recency of Year of Entry are violated for many group members. This would not be true if the cohort time-intervals $[s, t)$ were single years, but the numerical investigations in Section 4 of this paper show that residual-method estimates of foreign-born emigration based on single years of data are far too noisy to be practical, a conclusion that Population Division demographers had reached years ago.

For that reason, we propose here an approach to estimation based on aggregating single years of data but in a manner respecting the definitions of the emigration groups. Our proposal is to replace the estimator $\hat{R}_{[s,t)}^{(g)}$

in equation (12) by an estimator that aggregates similar single-year quantities for single years $[s+k-1, s+k)$, separately in numerator and denominator, with the denominator replaced by (20). The migration estimates $\hat{M}_{[s+k-1, s+k)}^{(g)}$ are to be defined exactly as in equation (8) using ACS_{s+k-1} and ACS_{s+k} . All the other \hat{N} and \hat{D} single-year estimates are defined from ACS_{s+k-1} . The modified estimator is

$$\hat{R}_{[s,t)}^{*(g)} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{t-s} \hat{M}_{[s-k+1, s+k)}^{(g)}}{\sum_{k=1}^{t-s} \left\{ \hat{N}_{s+k-1}^{(g), \text{ACS}_{s+k-1}} - \left(\hat{D}_{[s+k-1, s+k)}^{(g), \text{ACS}_{s+k-1}} + \hat{M}_{[s+k-1, s+k)}^{(g)} \right) / 2 \right\}} \quad (21)$$

5.4 Long Term Research

The goal of the methods proposed above, as well as further methods that may be developed through longer-term research, are to account for sources of error and find methods and models to reduce that error.

We conjecture that the imprecision and bias of emigration estimates due to allocation and imputation for missing data on citizenship, place of birth, and year of entry are sizable. It might be fruitful to develop modified model-based imputations for this purpose only. There is an ongoing project of Census Bureau staff to implement Bayesian imputation procedures along the lines of Akande et al. [2019], and this effort might be targeted specifically to the estimation of migration.

Life-table calculation of death rates is important in current methods and any conceivable alternatives. General-population life tables like those produced by NCHS are stable and accurate. However, it seems likely that mortality among recent immigrants (especially undocumented ones) differs markedly from both the general population and from the immigrant population from the same places with years of entry further in the past. Currently, the life-tables used in the emigration-group residual method are the Male and Female Hispanic life-tables published yearly by NCHS. We think that model-based statistical investigations concerning special-purpose emigration-group life tables is well-motivated, if methodology based on emigration groups is to be maintained in the future.

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